

Analysis of Language Errors in Student Scientific Writing

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Article History

Received: 28.10.2024

Accepted: 12.12.2024

Published: 10.01.2025

Abstract: This study aims to examine several writing errors or mistakes found in academic works by students in the process of completing their final assignments. The method used in this research involved analysing samples of students' theses through the lens of standard writing language criteria. The findings of this study reveal the following: 1) Errors in the use of capital letters occurred 48 times (30.20%). 2) Errors in the usage of prepositions *di*, *ke*, and *dari*, as well as the prefixes *di-* and *ke-*, occurred 13 times (8.17%), comprising 10 errors in prepositions and 3 errors in prefixes. 3) Errors in punctuation usage occurred 68 times (42.76%), including 12 errors in using periods (.), 22 errors in commas (,), 18 errors in hyphens (-), 3 errors in question marks (?), and 13 errors in colons (:). This study contributes to understanding common writing errors in academic works by highlighting the frequency and types of errors related to capitalization, prepositions, prefixes, and punctuation. The findings provide insights that can help educators design targeted interventions to improve students' academic writing quality.

Keywords: *Error Analysis, Language, Academic Writing.*

Cite this article:

Setyaningsih, S. I., (2025). Analysis of Language Errors in Student Scientific Writing. *ISAR Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Studies*, 3(1), 1-6.

Introduction

One of the elements of the Tri Dharma of higher education is the implementation of research for the academic community, including both lecturers and students. Every student is required to conduct research, at least in the form of a thesis.

A thesis is a scientific paper written by undergraduate students at the end of their studies based on research findings, literature reviews, or the development of a specific issue conducted thoroughly. It serves as a comprehensive and integrative representation of students' competence and performance in their field of study within their department or program. The thesis is integrated into the curriculum, where it is not only a requirement for completing their studies but also a course worth 6 credit hours (SKS).

As a scientific work, a thesis must meet established criteria. The information presented in a thesis must be factual, objective (unbiased), systematic (organized in a structured manner), use highly valid data, and the analysis and interpretation must be objective (Prayitno, 2004: 24). However, in practice, various issues arise during the preparation of scientific papers or final projects. The challenges faced by students include confusion in selecting topics, difficulty in determining a thesis title, challenges in finding literature and reading materials, limited financial resources, difficulty meeting with academic supervisors, rushing to meet munaqasyah (thesis defence) deadlines, and so on.

Additionally, many students lack writing skills, have insufficient academic abilities, or lack interest in research. These difficulties often lead to depression, low self-esteem, frustration, loss of motivation, procrastination in writing the thesis, and in some cases, decisions to abandon the thesis entirely.

Beyond these challenges, a critical aspect that deserves attention is the quality of scientific writing (theses) in terms of language. This quality is reflected in minimizing linguistic errors in students' theses. Ensuring this is crucial so that the ideas or concepts presented to readers can be accurately understood without neglecting linguistic rules. The same applies to the use of written Indonesian language.

The incorrect use of written Indonesian is referred to as linguistic errors. These errors include mistakes in punctuation and spelling, as outlined in the guidelines for Indonesian spelling, as well as errors in phonology, morphology, syntax, and paragraph construction (Tarigan and Suliastianingsih, 1998; Semi, 1990). The use of punctuation and spelling is regulated in the Pedoman Umum Ejaan Bahasa Indonesia (PUEBI) [General Guidelines for Indonesian Spelling] (2015), which is a revision of the Ejaan yang Disempurnakan (EYD) [Enhanced Spelling System] (1998). Every writer is expected to master the material in the EYD or PUEBI guidelines so that the meaning of each sentence is clear to the reader, avoiding ambiguity.

Given this context, it is crucial to evaluate the quality of students' academic works from a linguistic perspective. Scientific

writing demonstrates its quality when viewed through a linguistic lens, showing minimal or even no errors. By identifying the frequency of linguistic errors in students' academic works, follow-up actions can be taken to improve the quality of academic writing.

This paper aims to thoroughly examine the evaluation of one type of students' academic work, namely theses, particularly from a linguistic perspective. Evaluating the linguistic quality of students' theses is essential because it directly impacts the clarity and effectiveness of their academic communication. Identifying and addressing linguistic errors ensures that the ideas conveyed are accurate and meet the academic standards outlined in the General Guidelines for Indonesian Spelling (PUEBI).

This research highlights the types and frequency of linguistic errors in students' theses, providing valuable insights for improving academic writing quality. The findings serve as a reference for educators to design targeted training programs aimed at enhancing students' writing skills.

Literature Review

According to Yani, A. S., & Primandhika, R. B. (2023) in *Islamic Education Journal*, research explains that there are linguistic faults, according to the study's findings, with 65% of errors occurring in the morphology area, 20% in the syntax field, and 15% in the semantics field. 2) The reasons for these mistakes are the students' poor adherence to language rules, their ignorance, and the lecturers' inefficient teaching strategies. 3) Using educational resources that might increase students' enthusiasm to study and enhancing their diligence are two ways to remedy these linguistic faults.

According to Utomo, A. P. Y., Haryadi, H., Fahmy, Z., & Indramayu, A. (2019) in *Jurnal Sastra Indonesia*, research explain that the researchers concluded that language errors were found in the use of diction, phrases, and sentences. The errors that emerged included diction selection errors, phrase usage errors, and sentence ineffectiveness. The majority of diction selection errors involved the use of non-standard words and those not in accordance with the KBBI. Errors at the phrase level included inaccuracies in pairing words to form phrases and writing inaccuracies. As for sentence errors, they are due to the use of ineffective sentences, and some have ambiguous meanings.

According to Napitupulu, S. (2017) in *International Journal of Language and Linguistics*, researcher explain that the lexical, syntactic, grammatical, and substance mistakes. Students made 42.4% of grammatical errors, 26.7% of syntactic errors, 17.9% of content errors, and 13% of lexical errors, according to this study. It is determined from the discussion of the results that a significant number of mistakes were made by Indonesian students in this study as a result of first language transfer.

According to Pescante-Malimas, M. A., & Samson, S. C. (2017) in *IAFOR Journal of Language Learning*, researcher explain that in order to prepare graduating students for writing their thesis proposals, this study suggests that an intensive refresher writing course that concentrates on error-prone areas be held; that team teaching and other interventions be taken into consideration so that linguistic issues and content can be addressed together, as form and content go hand in hand; and, lastly, that a thesis editing guide or writing handbook be prepared, with a wealth of examples, practice exercises, and writing activities for instructors' and students' use.

Research Method

This study uses a qualitative descriptive approach with the aim of analyzing language errors in the thesis writing of students from the Mathematics Education Study Program at UIN Walisongo Semarang. The research sample consists of students' theses that have been submitted for the munaqasyah examination. These were selected using purposive sampling technique.

Data were collected by reading and analyzing students' theses to identify errors in three main aspects: the use of capital letters, prepositions and affixes, and punctuation. Each error found is recorded and categorized based on its type. Data analysis is conducted by counting the frequency of errors in each category, and the results are presented descriptively to illustrate the existing error patterns.

Result and Discussions

Scientific writing, writing is the result of composing in written form. Scientific writing consists of two words: "writing" and "scientific." According to the *Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia (KBBI)* or the *Indonesian Dictionary (2000:14)*, karya (work) is defined as a task, the result of an action, creation, or primarily a piece of written composition. Meanwhile, tulis (writing) in KBBI is defined as letters or numbers made with a pen (pencil, paint, etc.), something written or agreed upon, or that contains written text. Based on KBBI, scientific writing can be concluded as the result of composition in written form, presenting thoughts, observations, or reviews in a specific field, systematically arranged.

Scientific writing can also be described as written work discussing a particular issue based on systematic and directed observations. It is sometimes referred to as the expression of an individual's ideas presented in writing. While there are various definitions, they essentially convey the same meaning, which can be summarized as a person's work expressed in writing. One form of scientific writing is what is commonly referred to as a scientific paper.

A scientific paper is a written and published report presenting the results of research or studies conducted by an individual or a team, adhering to the principles and ethics of scholarship established and observed by the scientific community (Musfah, 2014:1). Scientific papers are often referred to as academic scientific papers or simply scientific papers.

Scientific papers are written works that present ideas, descriptions, or solutions to problems in a systematic manner, delivered objectively and honestly, using formal language, and supported by facts, theories, and/or empirical evidence. The purposes of scientific papers include conveying ideas, fulfilling academic assignments, discussing ideas in meetings, participating in competitions, and disseminating knowledge or research findings.

Scientific papers also serve as references, enhance knowledge, and spread scientific information. For the authors, writing scientific papers helps improve reading and writing skills, practice integrating ideas and presenting them systematically, broaden perspectives, and provide intellectual satisfaction while contributing to the advancement of scientific knowledge. One form of scientific paper is the thesis.

Analysis of linguistic errors, language holds significant importance in human life, as evidenced by its role as a tool for communication. In communication, humans can use either spoken or written language. In the context of written (scientific) language, writers are required to have greater skills compared to spoken language. This is intended to ensure that the ideas or concepts conveyed to readers are understood accurately without neglecting linguistic rules. The same applies to the use of written Indonesian.

The process of communication requires the use of correct written language in accordance with grammatical norms. This ensures that innovative ideas and concepts conveyed to others can be effectively understood. To achieve this, competence and precision are essential in the writing process. One way to continuously sharpen a writer's competence and precision is by analyzing existing writings.

When analyzing linguistic errors in scientific papers, several aspects need attention, including punctuation usage, spelling, phonology, morphology, syntax, and paragraph structure. By analyzing linguistic errors, one also learns various aspects of grammar.

Incorrect use of written Indonesian is referred to as linguistic errors. These errors include mistakes in punctuation usage, spelling, phonology, morphology, syntax, and paragraph structure. For instance, punctuation errors may involve incorrect placement of periods or commas. Spelling errors include improper use of loanwords, capitalization errors, etc. Tarigan and Sulistyarningsih (1998) state that linguistic errors in phonology include changes in phoneme pronunciation, phoneme omission, phoneme addition, and the alteration of diphthongs into single sounds or single phonemes.

Linguistic errors in morphology, according to Badudu (1982) and Tarigan and Sulistyarningsih (1998), are divided into three categories: (a) errors in affixation, (b) errors in reduplication, and (c) errors in compounding. Tarigan and Sulistyarningsih (1998) and Semi (1990) also note that linguistic errors in syntax involve errors in phrases, clauses, and sentences.

According to Kridalaksana (1998:45), phonology is a branch of linguistics that studies language sounds based on their function, also referred to as phonemics. Chaer (2008) states that phonology is a field of grammar that discusses specific language sounds, such as those in Indonesian, in the context of studying their function in distinguishing or identifying specific words. According to Tarigan and Sulistyarningsih (1998), linguistic error analysis in phonology involves changes in phoneme pronunciation, phoneme omission, phoneme addition, and the alteration of diphthongs into single sounds or phonemes. For example, phoneme omission occurs when *khusus* is pronounced as *kusus*. Phoneme addition occurs when *batin* is pronounced as *bathin*. Alteration of diphthongs, for example, occurs when *jadual* is pronounced as *jadwal*.

Furthermore, linguistic error analysis in morphology, according to Badudu (1982), is categorized into three groups: errors in affixation, reduplication, and compounding. Errors in affixation include instances where affixes that should be assimilated are not, affixes that should not be assimilated are assimilated, and shortening of morphemes such as *men-* to *n-*, *meny-* to *ny-*, *meng-* to *ng-*, and *menge-* to *nge-*. Additional errors occur in the processes of reduplication and compounding.

Apart from these, spelling and punctuation errors frequently appear. The use of punctuation and spelling is governed by EYD (Ejaan yang Disempurnakan) or the latest guideline, PUEBI (Pedoman Umum Ejaan Bahasa Indonesia). Thesis writers are expected to master the materials outlined in EYD/PUEBI. This ensures that the meaning of sentences is clear to readers and avoids ambiguity.

The Improved Indonesian Spelling (in accordance with the 2015 Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture) outlines three aspects: letter usage, letter writing, and word writing. However, in scientific writing, greater emphasis is given to the writing of letters and words (Sri Isnani, 2016: 10). The following is an explanation of these aspects. First, on the spec of letter writing. There are two important aspects that must be considered in writing letters in accordance with Indonesian Spelling (Ejaan Bahasa Indonesia/EBI), namely the use of capital letters, and the use of italics. The use of uppercase letters has the following rules: (a) used as the first letter of the initial word in a sentence, (b) used as the first letter of a direct quotation, (c) used as the first letter in expressions related to the name of God, pronouns for God, and the names of holy books, (d) used as the first letter of titles of honor, nobility, and religious titles when followed by a person's name, (e) used as the first letter in elements of job titles and ranks when followed by a person's name, used as a substitute for a specific person, or in the names of institutions and places, (f) used as the first letter in the components of a person's name, (g) used as the first letter of the names of nations, ethnic groups, and languages, (h) used as the first letter in the names of years, months, days, holidays, and historical events, (i) used as the first letter in geographical names that are proper nouns, (j) used as the first letter in the names of countries, government institutions, state organizations, and official documents, except when containing conjunctions, (k) used as the first letter in terms of kinship used as forms of address or references, (l) used as the first letter of the pronoun *Anda*, (m) used as the first letter in the abbreviations of titles, ranks, and forms of address, (n) used as the first letter of each element in fully repeated forms within the names of governmental institutions, state organizations, and official documents, (o) used as the first letter of all significant words in titles, magazines, newspapers, and other academic writings, except for prepositions and conjunctions.

While for italicized text is used for: (a) writing the titles of books, magazines, and newspapers cited in writing, (b) emphasizing and specifying letters, parts of words, words, and word groups, (c) writing scientific names or foreign phrases.

Secondly, there are several aspects that must be considered in writing words, including: writing root words, writing affixed words (derivative words), writing reduplicated words, writing compound words, writing pronouns (*ku, mu, nya, kau*), writing prepositions (*di, ke, dari*), writing articles (*si and sang*), writing particles (*lah, kah, tah, pun, and per*), writing abbreviations and acronyms, writing numbers and numerical symbols, writing monetary amounts, writing academic titles, writing official ranks and positions, and writing addresses.

Third, the use of punctuation marks in accordance with Indonesian spelling can be seen in various types of punctuation marks. Among them are : periods (.), commas (,), question marks (?), exclamation marks (!), semicolons (;), colons (:), ellipses (...), slashes (/), apostrophes ('), single quotation marks ('...'), double

quotation marks (“...”), hyphens (-), parentheses (), and square brackets [...]).

The language errors discussed here focus on spelling errors in students' academic writing. The selected academic writings are theses, which serve as students' final projects. The analysis was conducted on several theses written by students of the Mathematics Education program at Universitas Islam Negeri Walisongo Semarang. The analysis specifically targets spelling errors, including errors in letter usage, the use of capital and italic letters, word writing, the writing of loanwords, and punctuation use.

The theses were identified based on the types of errors. The identified spelling errors were then processed through data analysis techniques. Data was collected by reading each sentence, noting sentences with spelling errors, recording them on data cards, and analyzing them using qualitative descriptive techniques.

Based on the scope above, the results of the study on spelling errors in several theses of Mathematics Education students at Universitas Islam Negeri Walisongo Semarang revealed a total of 159 errors, comprising: (1) errors in the use of capital letters: 48 errors, (2) errors in the use of italic letters: 30 errors, (3) errors in the usage of the preposition *di* and the prefix *di-*: 13 errors, (4) errors in punctuation use: 68 cases, (5) no errors were found in the writing of loanwords.

The following table shows the frequency and percentage of spelling error types in the theses of Mathematics Education students at Universitas Islam Negeri Walisongo Semarang.

Table 1. Percentage of Spelling Errors in Students' Theses Mathematics Education Program, UIN Walisongo

No	Aspect of Spelling Error	Frequency	Percentage
1	Use of Capital Letters	48	30.20%
2	Italicized Text	30	18.87%
3	Usage of <i>di</i> (preposition) and <i>di-</i> (prefix)	13	8.17%
4	Use of Punctuation Marks	68	42.76%
5	Writing of Loanwords	-	-
Total	159	100%	

From the table above, it can be seen that the most frequent errors found in students' theses are related to punctuation usage. The details of these linguistic errors are presented as follows:

First, the use of capital letters, spelling errors in students' theses are partly caused by the improper use of capital letters. This study found 48 errors in the use of capital letters in theses written by Mathematics Education students of UIN Walisongo. These errors include a lack of understanding in using capital letters appropriately. The mistakes involve incorrect capitalization in the following areas: the first letter of a sentence, geographical names or names of countries, regions, and cities, borrowed foreign terms, the first letter of language names, and the first letter in a title or subtitle. The following examples illustrate errors in capital letter usage found in Mathematics Education students' theses at UIN Walisongo: (1)

“*Media berasal dari kata “Medium”, yang berasal dari bahasa latin “Medium” yang berarti “tengah” atau “sedang.”* (A/H-21/P-1/B-1), (2) “*Skripsi Nur Saifi dengan judul “Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran Matematika Berbasis Mobile Learning pada Materi Barisan dan Deret Kelas XII” NIM 095511031.*” (D/H-62/P-3/B-1).

In sentence (1), the letter m in Medium is capitalized, whereas it should be in lowercase, as it does not meet the criteria for capitalization. Additionally, the letter l in latin should be capitalized as it refers to the name of a language. Thus, the corrected sentence (1a) should be: (1a) “*Media berasal dari kata “medium”, yang berasal dari bahasa Latin “medium” yang berarti “tengah” atau “sedang.”*”

In sentence (2), the title of the thesis is written entirely in uppercase letters, whereas only the first letter of each word should be capitalized. Hence, the corrected sentence (2a) should be: (2a) “*Skripsi Nur Saifi dengan judul “Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran Matematika Berbasis Mobile Learning pada Materi Barisan dan Deret Kelas XII” NIM 095511031.*”

Second, italicized text. Spelling mistakes in students' theses are caused by the use of italicized text. In this study, there were 30 cases of errors in the use of italicized text in the theses of students of the Mathematics Education study program of UIN Walisongo. The errors in italicization mostly occurred in the writing of foreign terms or technical language. Below is data showing the mistakes in the use of italicized text in the theses of students from the Mathematics Education program at UIN Walisongo : (3) “..... completing the thesis entitled ‘The Implementation of the Think Pair Share Model and Concrete Media with a Scientific Approach to Improve Mathematics Learning Outcomes on the Topic of Ratios...’” (A/H-vii/P-1/B-4), (4) “For example, Accurat Hijri Calculator; an application to determine the Qomariah and Syamsiyah months as well as prayer times in several countries, Stellium, an application to determine the Gregorian month using weather knowledge and the position of the moon, Accurate...”

In example sentence (3), there is an error in the use of italicized text. The term Think Pair Share should be italicized because it is a foreign term (not in Indonesian). Therefore, the correct Indonesian spelling is: (3a) “..... completing the thesis entitled ‘The Implementation of the Think Pair Share Model and Concrete Media with a Scientific Approach to Improve Mathematics Learning Outcomes on the Topic of Ratios...’”

In example sentence (4), there are many terms related to applications and tools. The use of foreign names or terms, whether scientific, religious, technological, or otherwise, should be italicized. Hence, the correct Indonesian spelling is: (4a) “For example, Accurat Hijri Calculator; an application to determine the Qomariah and Syamsiyah months as well as prayer times in several countries, Stellium, an application to determine the Gregorian month using weather knowledge and the position of the moon, Accurate Time; an application.....”

Third, the use of prefixes (*di*), (*ke*), and prepositions (*di*, *ke*, and *dari*) are still errors in the thesis writing in distinguishing between *di-* and *ke-* as prefixes, as well as *di*, *ke*, and *dari* as prepositions. The prefixes *di-* and *ke-* are used with verbs and are written together with the root word. Meanwhile, the prepositions *di*, *ke*, and *dari* are used with nouns and indicate place-related information. In this analysis, there are 13 errors in the use of prefixes *di-*, *ke-*, and prepositions *di*,

ke, and dari. These consist of 10 errors involving the preposition di and 3 errors with the prefix di-, while there were no errors in the use of the prepositions ke and dari, or the prefix ke. Use of the Preposition (di) here is an example that shows a spelling error caused by the incorrect use of the preposition di. (5) “Soal diatas hanya diketahui sebuah data mengenai jenis pekerjaan orang tua siswa, tidak ada perintah/pertanyaan yang diajukan dalam soal.” (B/H-189/P-1/B-1).

In sentence (5), the preposition di in the word dibawah should be written separately from the following word. Therefore, the correct spelling for the preposition di in sentence (5) should be as follows: (5a) “Soal di atas hanya diketahui sebuah data mengenai jenis pekerjaan orang tua siswa, tidak ada perintah/pertanyaan yang diajukan dalam soal.”

Use of the Prefix di-, here is an example showing a spelling error caused by the incorrect use of the prefix di-. (6) “Untuk mencapai tujuan pendidikan maka pembelajaran perlu di desain dengan baik.” (C/H-1/P-2/B-2). In sentence (6), there is an error in the use of the prefix di- in the word di desain. The prefix di- should be written together with the following word because di- is a prefix, not a preposition. The di- prefix with a verb indicates a passive verb. Therefore, the correct spelling should be: (6a) “Untuk mencapai tujuan pendidikan maka pembelajaran perlu didesain dengan baik.”

Fourth, the use of punctuation. In this analysis, there were 68 errors in the use of punctuation, including 12 errors in the use of period (.), 22 errors in the use of comma (,), 18 errors in the use of semicolon (;), 3 errors in the use of question mark (?), and 13 errors in the use of colon (:). Meanwhile, there were no errors in the use of exclamation marks (!), single quotation marks ('...'), semicolons (;), double quotation marks (“...”), or slashes (/).

Use of periods (.), the data showing spelling errors caused by improper use of periods. (7) “Hasil Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMS) di tahun 2011 melaporkan bahwa prestasi matematika siswa Indonesia berada di peringkat 38 dari 42 negara peserta.” (B/H-4/P2/B-8). In sentence (7), there is an error in the use of the period. The period is placed after the last letter of the sentence without a space. The correct spelling for this sentence is: (7a) “Hasil Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMS) di tahun 2011 melaporkan bahwa prestasi matematika siswa Indonesia berada di peringkat 38 dari 42 negara peserta.”

Use of commas (,), data showing spelling errors caused by improper use of commas (,). (8) “Selain itu peserta didik diminta untuk membandingkan dua jawaban yang ada kemudian mengidentifikasi jawaban yang benar beserta alasan yang tepat.” (B/H-187/P-1/B-3). In sentence (8), a comma is missing. A comma should be used to separate elements in a list or enumeration. The correct spelling for this sentence is as follows: (8a) “Selain itu, peserta didik diminta untuk membandingkan dua jawaban yang ada, kemudian mengidentifikasi jawaban yang benar beserta alasan yang tepat.”

Use of hyphens (-), the data showing spelling errors caused by improper use of hyphens (-). (9) “Kebermaknaan yang di maksud adalah pernyataan konsep - konsep dalam bentuk bagan, diagram atau peta sehingga tampak keterkaitan diantara konsep - konsep yang diberikan.” (A/H-34/P-1/B-3). In sentence (9), there is an error in the use of hyphens. A hyphen should not have spaces on either side. The correct spelling for this sentence is: (9a) “Kebermaknaan

yang dimaksud adalah pernyataan konsep-konsep dalam bentuk bagan, diagram atau peta sehingga tampak keterkaitan diantara konsep-konsep yang diberikan.”

Use of question marks (?), the data showing spelling errors caused by improper use of question marks (?). (10) “Apakah pembelajaran dengan menggunakan model pembelajaran inquiri berbantu alat peraga “Basic Statistic Counter” efektif terhadap peningkatan hasil belajar siswa kelas IX pada materi statistika SMP NU Hasanudin 07 Semarang tahun pelajaran 2015/2016.” (C/H-6/P-2/B-2). In sentence (10), there is an error in punctuation. A statement (affirmative) should use a period (.), an exclamation should use an exclamation mark (!), and a question should use a question mark (?). A question is indicated by starting with a question word (what, why, how, when, where). The correct spelling for this sentence is: (10a) “Apakah pembelajaran dengan menggunakan model pembelajaran inquiri berbantu alat peraga “Basic Statistic Counter” efektif terhadap peningkatan hasil belajar siswa kelas IX pada materi statistika SMP NU Hasanudin 07 Semarang tahun pelajaran 2015/2016?”

Use of colons (:), the data showing spelling errors caused by improper use of colons (:). (11) “Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk menjawab rumusan masalah: apakah penerapan Think Pair Share (TPS) dan media konkrit dengan pendekatan saintifik pada materi perbandingan dapat meningkatkan keaktifan dan hasil belajar peserta didik kelas VII C semester II MTs.” (A/H-v/P-2/B-16). In sentence (11), a colon is incorrectly placed after a complete statement when it is followed by a list or description. Additionally, the colon is placed at the end of the sentence without a space. The correct spelling for this sentence is: (11a) “Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk menjawab rumusan masalah: apakah penerapan Think Pair Share (TPS) dan media konkrit dengan pendekatan saintifik pada materi perbandingan dapat meningkatkan keaktifan dan hasil belajar peserta didik kelas VII C semester II MTs.”.

Conclusion

The results of this analysis indicate that spelling errors are still found in the theses of students from the Mathematics Education Program, Faculty of Science and Technology, Walisongo State Islamic University Semarang. Therefore, an overview of these types of errors can serve as input, especially for students, to be more meticulous in their spelling usage. Additionally, it can provide insights for thesis supervisors or authorities in the field of linguistics to investigate the reasons behind the persistent spelling errors. This study recommends that students improve their attention to spelling accuracy in academic writing to enhance the quality of their theses. Supervisors and linguistic educators should also address the underlying causes of persistent spelling errors through targeted guidance and workshops.

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